

INFLUENCE OF PULSE-ARC WELDING WITH CONSUMABLE ELECTRODE ON STRESS-STRAIN STATE OF STICK JOINTS OF ALUMINUM ALLOY Al-Mg-Mn

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ABSTRACT

The work is devoted to the study of the residual stress-strain state (SSS) of butt joints of aluminum alloy samples of the Al-Mg-Mn system. Based on the technological experiments, finite element modeling of butt joints of aluminum alloy 1561 samples with a thickness of 5 mm obtained by pulsed arc welding with a consumable electrode (MIG welding) was performed. The effect of this welding process on the residual stress-strain state (SSS) of the resulting joints was predicted. Empirical determination of residual deformations by their micrometric measurements showed that the calculated data differ from the measured ones by an average of 5...10%, which is acceptable for the problem being solved.

Keywords: pulsed arc welding with a consumable electrode, aluminum alloy 1561 of the Al-Mg-Mn system, stress-strain state.

Welding deformations and residual stresses are the most complex thermal phenomena occurring during fusion welding. In order to fully understand the characteristic features of welding deformations, it is necessary to conduct a series of studies using thermal analysis and mathematical modeling [1]. Numerous computational and experimental studies (e.g. [2-3]) were conducted to study the mechanisms of occurrence of welding deformations and residual stresses. In this case, analytical and numerical methods were used to predict and quantitatively assess the influence of deformations and residual stresses during welding [4]. However, accurate prediction of deformations is very difficult even for simple welded structures and even more difficult for the design of objects whose elements are connected sequentially. In this regard, one of the important tasks is to predict residual stresses and deformations in MIG welding of aluminum alloys [5]. This is due to the large volumes of industrial application of the MIG welding process in the manufacture of structures from aluminum alloys [6].

The aim of the work is to perform finite element modeling of butt joints of samples of aluminum alloy

1561 of the Al-Mg-Mn system, obtained by pulsed arc welding with a consumable electrode (MIG welding), based on technological experiments, allowing to predict the influence of this welding process on the residual stress-strain state (RSS) of the obtained joints.

To achieve the set goal, the following **tasks** were solved to predict the stress-strain state of joints of aluminum alloy 1561 samples obtained by MIG welding:

1. Determine longitudinal and transverse stresses.
2. Determine longitudinal and transverse deformations.
3. Determine displacements from the plane.

Technological experiments were carried out using welding equipment, which included: a power source for pulsed MIG welding (unipolar pulse frequency of about 300 Hz) with a welding wire feed mechanism designed for welding currents up to 400 A, a torch for automatic MIG welding, an anthropomorphic robot manipulator in whose hand the welding torch was fixed, welding and assembly equipment for rigid fixation of welded samples (Fig. 1). Alloy 1561 plates measuring 300×100×5 mm were used as welded samples.

Fig. 1. Robotic experimental complex.

In mathematical modeling of the MIG welding process, to solve the associated thermomechanical problem, it is necessary to take into account the volumetric nature of the heat source. For this, we use the model of a distributed volumetric heat source proposed

by J. Goldak (Fig. 2) [7]. The analytical model of J. Goldak specifies a normal (according to Gauss) distribution of the power density of the heat source in the volume of the body, which has the shape of a double ellipsoid [8].

Fig. 2. Model of a volumetric welding heat source J. Goldak [7].

The temperature field $T(x, y, z, t)$ of such a distributed volumetric heat source satisfies the differential nonlinear equation of heat conduction at any point of the body, described in the work [8]. As a result of solving this equation, we obtain the density q of the thermal power of the volumetric source in the welded material:

$$q = 4Q \left(\frac{\sqrt{A_1 A_2 B C}}{\sqrt{\pi^3 (\sqrt{A_1} + \sqrt{A_2})}} \right), \quad (1)$$

where $Q = \eta IU$ is the effective thermal power of the heating source taking into account the efficiency of MIG welding ($\eta = 0,6$). The values of the coefficients A_1, A_2, B, C are (Fig.1):

$$A_1 = \frac{3}{a_f^2}, A_2 = \frac{3}{a_r^2}, B = \frac{3}{b^2}, C = \frac{3}{c^2}. \quad (2)$$

To perform the calculation and obtain the distribution of the parameters of the residual stress-strain state (RSS) of a symmetrical butt welded joint of alloy 1561 with a thickness of $\delta = 5$ mm during automatic MIG welding, the data presented in Table 1 were used. Knowing the welding mode and the geometric dimensions of the weld pool, a predictive modeling of the MIG welding process of butt joints of alloy 1561 was performed using the finite element method.

Table 1.

Parameters of the mode and the result of MIG welding of alloy 1561 ($\delta=5$ mm).

Mode parameters	Welding pool		
Welding current 253 A	Length, mm	Width, mm	Depth, mm
Arc voltage 25.8 V	25.6	13.5	5.0
Welding speed 10 mm/s			

The calculation of the residual SSS parameters was performed with the action of assembly and welding equipment in the form of two solid plates located on a 40 mm base relative to the weld, which rigidly fixed the welded plates in the plane [8]. Fig. 3 shows the fields of longitudinal stresses in the welded joint at the time of the equipment action (Fig. 3,a) and after the welded joint unfastening (Fig. 3,b). When the equipment is in action, high stresses of ~ 300 MPa are observed in the

weld area and practically zero stresses of $\sim 20 \dots 23$ MPa in the area of the equipment action. Unfastening of the welded joint leads to stress redistribution. In the weld area, the level of residual stresses decreases to ~ 200 MPa with the formation of compressive stresses outside the plastic deformation zone of the order of -48 MPa with the subsequent transition to the tensile zone of ~ 5.3 MPa at the ends parallel to the weld.

Fig. 3. Fields of residual longitudinal stresses: a) – in rigid equipment; b) – after unfastening from the equipment.

The fields of transverse normal stresses under the action of the fixing equipment (Fig. 4,a) are similar to the fields of longitudinal stresses (Fig. 3,a) and differ slightly in magnitude to the downside of approximately

274 MPa. Unfastening of the welded joint (Fig. 4,b) leads to a significant (up to 93%) decrease in the level of transverse stresses (from 274 MPa to ~ 20 MPa).

Fig. 4. Fields of residual transverse stresses: a) – in rigid equipment; b) – after unfastening from the equipment.

When the fixing equipment is removed, the field of residual equivalent plastic deformations, determined according to von Mises [9], has clearly defined areas with zero deformation values in the areas of contact of the equipment with the plates (Fig. 5). Highly heated

areas of the welded joint, free from equipment during welding, are characterized by a rather sharp increase in plastic deformations, reaching a maximum on the axis of the weld.

Fig. 5. Field of residual equivalent plastic deformations according to von Mises.

As can be seen from Fig. 6(a), the action of the fixing fixture during welding and cooling led to a minimal (about -0.08...0.01 mm) shortening of the fixed areas of the welded joint and maximum shortenings of the beginning (~-0.47 mm) and end (~-0.44 mm) of the weld. After unfastening from the fixture (Fig. 6,b), the shortenings generally increased: about -0.08...-0.03 mm in the areas where the fixture was in effect, and up

to ~-0.54 mm at the beginning and ~-0.49 mm at the end of the weld. Along the width of the welded joint, the longitudinal shortenings are distributed unevenly both during the action of the fixture and after its removal: the welded central part received the greatest shortening displacements due to the effect of the high-gradient temperature field of the welding arc on it.

Fig. 6. Fields of residual longitudinal displacements in a welded joint: a) – in rigid equipment; b) – after unfastening from the equipment.

The transverse displacement fields in the presence of the fixing rigid equipment (Fig. 7, a) and after its removal (Fig. 7, b) allow us to verify the practically uniform transverse shortening along the entire length of the weld in the area of the weld joint free from the

equipment ~ 0.41 mm - with the equipment in effect and somewhat more ~ 0.43 mm - after its removal. The nature of the distribution of transverse shortenings on the reverse side of the welded joint is identical to the nature of their distribution on the front side of the joint.

Fig. 7. Fields of residual transverse displacements in a welded joint: a) – in rigid equipment; b) – after unfastening from the equipment.

The displacements from the plane of the welded sheets in the presence of rigid equipment are within the boundaries of the area free of fastenings, their value is ~ 0.13 mm with a maximum at the weld axis of ~ 0.38 mm. In the areas of contact of the welded plates with the equipment, the displacements are minimal ~ 0.05

mm. After the welded joint is loosened, there is some expansion of the zone with displacement values of ~ 0.11 mm along the entire length of the joint, and the displacement values at the weld axis do not exceed ~ 0.37 mm.

Fig. 8. Fields of residual displacements from the plane: a) – in rigid equipment; b) – after unfastening from the equipment.

The displacements on the front side are positive and greater in magnitude than on the back side, where they are negative and less than -0.1 mm. Such a distribution indicates the presence of a deflection of the longitudinal axis of the welded joint with the formation of a "bulge" in the middle of the joint and "houses" at the ends of the welded joint due to transverse shrinkage in the weld area.

Fig. 9. Measurements of deformations of butt welded joints.

The reduction of residual stresses during the unfastening of the welded sample from the welding and assembly equipment is associated with the impossibility of free expansion of the metal during welding in all directions due to the fixing equipment. Thus, the heated metal will primarily expand into the gap between the welded plates, and the lack of the possibility for free transverse shortening in width during the cooling of the already welded sheets will contribute to the occurrence of corresponding tensile transverse stresses, and, as a consequence, the formation of a flat stress state in the welded joint after welding.

The main reason for the formation of residual welding stresses are uncompensated residual plastic deformations, which are unevenly distributed in the cross-section of the welded joint.

For the front and back surfaces of the welded joint, the nature of the change in equivalent deformations is practically the same, with the exception of points lying on the axis of the weld. On the front surface, at points on the axis of the weld along the entire length of the welded joint, with the exception of the end areas, we observe peak values of deformation of ~ 0.074 , while on the back side at the same points the value of equivalent deformation is ~ 0.018 . Exceeding the equivalent defor-

To verify the above calculation assumptions, an empirical determination of residual deformations was carried out by micrometric measurements (Fig. 9). Such measurements showed that the calculated data differ from the measured data by an average of $5\text{...}10\%$. Such accuracy is satisfactory for predicting technological processes [10]. It can be assumed that the accuracy of determining stresses using the developed method is approximately the same.

mations on the front surface by ~ 4 times indicates uneven heating of the metal along the thickness and its "squeezing" onto the front side of the joint.

Conclusions.

1. When the fixing equipment is in effect, high (~ 300 MPa) longitudinal stresses and virtually zero ($\sim 20\text{...}23$ MPa) longitudinal stresses are observed in the weld area. Unfastening of the weld joint leads to a 30-35% decrease in residual stresses in the weld area and the formation of compressive stresses of about -48 MPa outside the plastic deformation zone. The fields of transverse normal stresses when the fixing equipment is in effect (~ 274 MPa) are similar to the fields of longitudinal stresses. Unfastening of the weld joint leads to a significant (up to 93%) decrease in the level of transverse stresses.

2. Residual longitudinal displacements of the welded joint areas fixed by the tooling are about $-0.08\text{...}0.01$ mm; after unfastening from the tooling, the shortenings generally increased to $-0.08\text{...}0.03$ mm. Transverse shortenings along the seam length of the welded joint area free from the tooling under the action of the tooling are ~ 0.41 mm, after its removal ~ 0.43 mm. The nature of the distribution of transverse short-

enings on the reverse side of the welded joint is identical to the nature of their distribution on the front side of the joint.

3. The displacements from the plane of welded flat samples of alloy 1561 in the presence of rigid equipment are ~0.13 mm within the boundaries of the area free of fastenings, reaching a maximum of ~0.38 mm on the weld axis. In the areas of contact of the welded samples with the equipment, the displacements are minimal - ~0.05 mm. After the welded joint is loosened, some expansion of the zone occurs with displacement values of ~0.11 mm along the entire length of the joint, and the displacement values on the weld axis do not exceed ~0.37 mm.

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